

Practice Abstract no. 53

FOODITY - Open Call #2 project - TRACE-IT

The FOODITY project launched the second of its two open calls in May 2024 and closed in July 2024. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in November 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is "TRACE-IT: Transparent AgriFood Chain for Ethical and Innovative Traceability."

Profile

Project acronym / title	TRACE-IT Transparent AgriFood Chain for Ethical and Innovative Traceability
Partners (country)	Trusty S.r.l. Società Benefit (Italy), Department of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences of the Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro (Italy)
Project area	Services

Context

The European food industry faces a complex challenge in complying with the EU Green Deal's demanding new regulations, specifically the European Union Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD). These mandates require robust traceability and sustainability verification across intricate global supply chains, particularly for vulnerable commodities like cocoa and coffee.

Simultaneously, the industry must respond to increasing consumer demand for transparency in food sourcing, while also navigating the complexities of GDPR compliance in data collection, especially concerning small-scale producers. This requires a delicate balance between comprehensive data gathering, respecting individual privacy rights, and upholding data sovereignty. Furthermore, effective citizen engagement is vital, as consumers increasingly seek to actively understand and influence the sustainability of their food choices.

Yet, existing traceability solutions are often inadequate, suffering from data fragmentation, limited interoperability, poor engagement with small-scale producers, and insufficient mechanisms for consumer interaction. These deficiencies prevent the industry from efficiently and affordably meeting the new regulatory standards and hinder the development of GDPR-compliant, citizen-centric approaches to food system transparency.

The TRACE-IT project offers an innovative blockchain-based platform that integrates all of the supply-chain actors and user-friendly interfaces to create a comprehensive, GDPR-compliant traceability solution. The solution positions itself as one of the first solutions in Europe to focus explicitly on GDPR compliance while addressing the data sharing requirements of EUDR and CSDDD regulations. This is considered a vital step as many small-scale farmers and other small actors may be sharing data without ownership or knowledge of its destination to comply with these regulations.

Objectives

The main objective of the TRACE-IT project is to create a transparent, sustainable, and compliant food supply chain through advanced traceability technology, integrating market dynamics and environmental impact assessments, while ensuring GDPR compliance and citizen engagement.

Specific objectives of the project include:

- Develop an advanced end-to-end traceability platform that ensures compliance with European Green Deal Regulation (starting from EUDR and CSDDD), integrating blockchain, AI, GDPR-compliant cloud based platform for secure data sharing (dataU) and centralised repository that makes data accessible for stakeholders and researchers (data lake).
- Empower small-scale farmers and cooperatives with digital tools for sustainable practices documentation and direct market access.
- Enable food companies to verify and communicate the sustainability of their supply chains to consumers and regulators.
- Conduct in-depth market analysis and consumer preference studies to guide sustainable product development and marketing strategies.
- Perform Life Cycle Impact Assessments (LCIA) to evaluate and improve the environmental sustainability of food products.
- Promote data sovereignty and ethical data sharing across the supply chain, including consumers, to enhance data transparency and empower sustainable product choices.

Impact

TRACE-IT foresees the following project impact:

1. **Enhanced data collection and analysis**, facilitated by an easy to use data collection app, the integration of satellite imagery and industrial systems for automated data collection and monitoring, and implementation of blockchain technology to ensure data integrity and traceability.

2. **Improved decision-making and market insights**, providing stakeholders with real-time insights on sustainability performance and compliance risks, and performing lifecycle impact assessments to evaluate the environmental sustainability of products.
3. **Citizen data rights and engagement**, by implementing a user-centric data management system that gives all stakeholders, including small-scale farmers and consumers, control over their personal and business data. Furthermore, by creating mechanisms for active citizen participation in shaping sustainable food systems.
4. **Regulatory compliance and data sovereignty**, by ensuring adherence to EUDR and CSDDD regulations through comprehensive data collection and reporting. Also, by implementing GDPR-compliant data sharing mechanisms, addressing the current issue of small-scale farmers sharing data without ownership or knowledge of its destination.
5. **Market analysis and consumer behaviour**, by conducting in-depth market segmentation to identify specific groups of consumers interested in sustainability attributes, and by providing insights for developing effective marketing strategies and sustainable production practices.

